

The procedure takes 1.5 d. From 500 g infected plants without roots, current methods yielded 1 ml of purified preparation with an absorbance at 260 m ranging from 1.0 to 2.8. With 300 g materials, the modified method yielded 1 ml, with absorbance ranging from 13 to 20. The ratio of absorbance

at 260 nm and 280 nm of the purified virus ranged from 1.70 to 1.75.

Purified preparations were injected into rabbits, and antiserum with a titer of 1/1280 in the ring interface precipitin test was obtained.

We also attempted to improve the purification method for rice tungro

bacilliform virus (RTBV). Without using driselase and organic solvent, the virus yield was not significantly improved. The rabbit antiserum to RTBV had a titer of 1/640. The antisera did not cross-react and did not react with healthy rice extracts in ELISA and the latex test. □

Insect management

Severe outbreak of green leafhopper (GLH) in Cuddapah District, Andhra Pradesh, India

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Nearly 50,000 ha of transplanted-irrigated rice is grown in Cuddapah district in wet season. Predominant cropping is rice followed by groundnut during winter-summer in canal water area, and a single rice crop in tankfed areas depending on rainfall. Main cultivars are Phalguna, Mahsuri, and NLR9672, with some NLR9674, IET7575, IR50, and IR20. Low humidity, high temperature, and scant rainfall (400-500 mm) reduce insect and disease incidence.

Cuddapah received good rainfall the last 2 wk of Oct and first 2 wk of Nov 1984, when hopperburn and numerous GLH were observed in 30-40% of cropped area on most cultivars. This was the first report of GLH outbreak from Cuddapah. The crop was in tillering to active tillering phases. A 15-village survey showed nymphs and

adults (30-150/hill), with adults more numerous.

IR20 and IR50 had fewer GLH and no hopperburn (see table). Phalguna, Mahsuri, NLR9672, and NLR9674 showed hopperburn in patches. Mahsuri showed 100-150 GLH/hill. IET7575, a brown planthopper-resistant variety, had 20-40/hill.

This outbreak appeared due to migration from adjoining Mellore

district after harvest of the 1984 summer rice crop (May-Aug) where about 20,000 ha were devastated by tungro (RTV).

The early crop, planted in late Aug, escaped infestation but the late crop showed severe infestation. Despite heavy GLH population, there was no RTV, even though adjacent Mellore and Prakasam districts had severe RTV the same season. □

Parasitoids of leafhopper (LF) pupae from Haryana, India

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Four parasitoids of pupae of rice LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenée) were

recorded at RRS during 1987 kharif. They were *Xanthopimpla flavolineata* (Cameron), *Xanthopimpla* sp. (Ichneumonidae), *Brachymeria* sp. nr. *lasus* (Walker) (Chalcididae), and *Tetrastichus ayyari* Rohwer (Eulophidae). Parasitism rates are shown in the table. □

Parasitism rates of 4 parasitoids of LF pupae. Haryana, India, 1987.

Days after transplanting	Parasitism (%)			
	<i>Xanthopimpla flavolineata</i>	<i>Xanthopimpla</i> sp.	<i>Brachymeria lasus</i>	<i>Tetrastichus ayyari</i>
55	23.3	—	—	—
65	7.5	1.0	1.5	2.5
75	10.7	2.0	—	—
85	20.0	—	—	—

Severity of GLH on common rice cultivars in farmers' fields in A. P., India, 1984.

Cultivar	Crop phase	GLH (no./hill)
Mahsuri	Active tillering	100-150
Phalguna	Active tillering	30-55
IET1515	Active tillering	20-40
NLR9612	Initial tillering	45-75
NLR9674	Initial tillering	45-75
IR50	Panicle emergence	10-15
IR20	Grain hardening	5-10

An expert system for insecticide control of brown planthopper (BPH)

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Using insecticides to control BPH can promote rather than limit BPH

population development. Insecticides can kill natural enemies that keep BPH populations below serious levels. Insecticides must be used only when this natural balance has been lost, and then must be timed carefully.

An expert system (see figure) can show when insecticide use is appropriate. Expert systems are computer programs that offer information or advice as a human